

METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES BY DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an overview of recent work at Ford and The University of Michigan developing insights and tools to assist in the selection or "design" of particle reinforced metal composites. It overviews bounds for approximating elastic and thermal properties. Strength-related properties such as tensile, creep and fatigue are treated using a combination of continuum mechanics models, systematic experimentation and microstructural control. The relative contributions of direct versus indirect strengthening are discussed. The issue of fabricated component cost is treated as well as an example of the application of this "methodology" to design of a particle reinforced metal composite for a connecting rod.

INTRODUCTION

Particle reinforced metal matrix composites are an important new class of materials which have potential for utilization in a wide variety of applications (1). One of the important attributes of these and other composite materials is the ability to select the individual elements of these materials such that the combined properties of the composite are specifically tailored for a particular application. The goal of this paper is to overview recent work of the authors aimed at development of insights or tools which will assist the material scientist in selecting or "designing" an appropriate particle reinforced metal matrix composite for a particular application. Such tools could be eventually employed in composite material selection approaches such as those proposed by Ashby (2). The focus here will be on elastic and thermal properties, as well as strength-related properties, specifically tensile strength, creep and fatigue. Two important approaches will be emphasized in this paper, the use of modeling or bounds to predict properties of composite materials and the careful control of matrix alloy and microstructure to allow rational comparisons between unreinforced alloys and their various composites. This paper covers investigations of particle reinforced aluminum composites conducted at Ford and The University of Michigan. Given the scope of this paper, the reference list is aimed primarily at providing more detailed descriptions of our work. These papers provide references to the many other important contributions to the particle reinforced metals knowledge base.

ELASTIC AND THERMAL PROPERTIES

The approach favored for determining elastic and thermal properties of composites is computing the upper and/or lower bounds as a function of volume fraction for the appropriate phase geometry. In most practical examples, at a given volume fraction, the upper bound is sufficiently close to the lower bound that the uncertainty in the computed

composite property is less than other uncertainties such as errors in the input parameters. It is also possible to calculate these values using finite element analysis (FEA), however this is generally not necessary for elastic and thermal properties due to their linearity. One can also use effective medium approximations for a number of properties, although we usually prefer applying bounds (when they exist) since they are not subject to approximation and they indicate the maximum possible error in the computed property. Additionally, the computation of the bounds is simple, being only slightly more difficult than calculating an effective medium approximation. Finally, it should be emphasized that the rule of mixtures (ROM) is seldom accurate and generally should not be used.

Elastic properties

Since we assume that each constituent of the composite is isotropic, only two parameters are needed to describe the elastic properties of each constituent. Let Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio be E_m and ν_m for the matrix and E_p and ν_p for the particle, respectively. For either constituent the bulk modulus K and the shear modulus G can be related to E and ν . We let ϕ be the volume fraction of particles. If there is no information about the constituent geometry (particle shape, arrangement, etc), other than the composite is isotropic over all and homogeneous on a macroscopic scale, the best bounds that can be given are those of Hashin and Shtrikman. For the shear modulus the lower (G_-) and upper (G_+) bounds are (3)

$$G_- = G_m + \frac{\phi}{1 / (G_p - G_m) + 6(1 - \phi)(K_m + 2G_m) / 5G_m(3K_m + 4G_m)}, \quad (1)$$

$$G_+ = G_p + \frac{1 - \phi}{1 / (G_m - G_p) + 6\phi(K_p + 2G_p) / 5G_p(3K_p + 4G_p)}$$

The bounds on the bulk modulus are similar. Sharper bounds, that is, bounds that are closer together are the third-order bounds (4). These bounds assume that the particles are all spheres of the same size and are arranged in one of several possible configurations, for example, random but not overlapping.

In Fig. 1, we plot Young's modulus versus volume fraction of reinforcing phase for Al/SiC. The dashed curves in this figure marked HS are the upper and lower Hashin-Shtrikman bounds and the solid lines marked "Th. Ord." are the third-order bounds. The bounds on E are calculated from the bounds on K and G . The line marked ROM is the rule of mixtures estimate, which is a linear extrapolation between the end points. It is inaccurate and should not be used. Data taken from the literature are shown for comparison. It is seen that the lower bounds, either Hashin-Shtrikman or third-order appear to represent the data rather well. The upper Hashin-Shtrikman bound considerably overestimates the modulus. Bounds on Poisson's ratio ν for Al/SiC are shown in Fig. 2.

Thermal properties

The thermal conductivity of the composite, κ , can be determined from the rather sharp Hashin-Shtrickman bounds for the coefficient of thermal conductivity in the absence of boundary resistance. Typical examples are shown in Fig. 3. Unlike other physical properties considered in this chapter, the interface between the matrix and the inclusion can not be neglected when treating thermal conductivity. This is because all interfaces exhibit a thermal boundary resistance. Even if the surface is perfect, there is an inherent boundary effect due to the phenomena called Kapitza resistance, which arises from the acoustic mismatch between phonons in different materials. If one material is a metal, then the effect can be even more pronounced because heat is predominantly carried by electrons in the metal and

Figure 1. Bounds for Young's Modulus (3).

Figure 2. Bounds for Poisson's ratio.

they must somehow couple to the phonons in the adjacent non-metallic material. To include such effects an effective medium theory (EMT) has been developed and verified for a variety of materials (5). The EMT for thermal conductivity of the composite, K , gives:

$$\frac{K}{K_m} = \frac{[K_p(1+2\alpha) + 2K_m] + 2\phi[K_p(1-\alpha) - K_m]}{[K_p(1+2\alpha) + 2K_m] - \phi[K_p(1-\alpha) - K_m]}, \quad (2)$$

where K_m and K_p are the thermal conductivities of the metal and the ceramic particle, respectively, ϕ is the volume fraction of particles, and the dimensionless parameter α is defined by

$$\alpha = \frac{R_{Bd}K_m}{r}. \quad (3)$$

Here r is the radius of the particles, which are assumed to be spherical and monodisperse, and R_{Bd} is the thermal boundary resistance for particular two-phase combinations (5). Using appropriate values for these terms, we find that adding particles of SiC with radii $< 2.5 \mu\text{m}$ to Al actually *decreases* the thermal conductivity of the composite relative to the unreinforced aluminum. From more detailed analysis, it can be shown that the SiC particles should have a radius of $10 \mu\text{m}$ or more if the full benefit of the dispersed constituent is to be realized.

Bounds can also be computed for coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) since there is an exact analytic expression that relates it to the bulk moduli of the composite and its constituents (3). In Fig. 4 we show the computations for CTE using the HS bounds on K . The upper bound more closely approximates the CTE of the composite if the ceramic constituent is in the form of particles. A thorough analysis of the thermal expansion of metal-matrix composites has been given by Shen, Needleman, and Suresh (6).

Figure 4. Bounds for thermal conductivity (5). Figure 6. Bounds for coefficient of thermal expansion.

STRENGTH-RELATED PROPERTIES

As shown above, properties such as elastic modulus and thermal expansion coefficient are comparatively simple and can be readily predicted using bounds. In contrast, our ability to predict strength-related properties such as yield strength, creep and fatigue resistance is more limited. To understand strength-related properties we separate the influence of reinforcement into two factors, direct and indirect strengthening. **Direct strengthening** results from the stress redistribution which results when a high modulus phase is present in a lower modulus matrix, leading to reduced plastic deformation in the latter. In general, direct strengthening can be modeled quite well using continuum mechanics solutions. A convenient way to model direct strengthening is the use of unit cell models solved using finite element analysis. Although some limitations exist, we believe that the unit-cell models are adequate for all but the most concentrated particulate composites. **Indirect strengthening** arises from changes in the matrix microstructure due to the presence of the reinforcement and can lead indirectly to changes in the overall properties of the aggregate. In contrast to direct strengthening, indirect effects are not readily predictable and can only be understood at present by systematic empirical investigation. Microstructural features such as grain size, precipitate size and structure and dislocation substructure have a strong influence on properties and can also be altered in significant ways by incorporation of a reinforcement particle. Two important examples of this are the grain size reduction which frequently occurs in particle reinforced metals (7) and "accelerated aging" (8). The degree of indirect strengthening which can occur is highly specific to the alloy/reinforcement/fabrication technology under consideration. In some cases, the contributions to strengthening due to indirect effects can be substantially greater than those due to direct composite strengthening. These indirect contributions can lead to either property improvements or property degradation.

Tensile Strength

The incorporation of high-modulus particles such as SiC in a metal such as aluminum, generally leads to an increase in tensile strength. To understand the relative importance of direct versus indirect strengthening, recent results for 2080Al/SiCp are given. An indication of the importance of matrix microstructure, in this case precipitate spacing, on yield strength is shown in Figure 5. The precipitate spacing was altered by various thermal-mechanical

treatments (see Ref. 9 for details). This figure shows that by holding precipitate spacing constant, indirect effects due to SiC particle size and volume fraction can be isolated. Thus the substantial increase in strength which results from a decrease in particle size exhibited in Fig. 5 is presumably a result of direct strengthening. Similarly, Figure 6 shows the influence of increasing volume fraction of SiC particles on the yield strength of 2080 Al. In this figure, the thermal-mechanical treatments have been carefully controlled to ensure that the aluminum matrix microstructure is identical in each material. Also shown Figure 6 are the predictions of unit cell models which agree quite well with the experimental results. The unit cell modelling was conducted assuming that the constitutive properties of the matrix were the same in all the materials and taking into account the residual strains which occur on cooling from solution treatment (10). We have also verified these unit cell models by neutron diffraction measurement of both residual and applied stresses (11). Direct composite strengthening arises from the differences in modulus between the particle and matrix, thus an increase in the ratio of particle modulus to matrix modulus leads to an increase in strength of the composite. FEA modeling of stress-strain response has shown that the increased work hardening often observed in particle reinforced metals can be understood in terms of a continual increase in the volume of material which has undergone plastic deformation.

Figure 5. Influence of precipitate spacing and SiC particle size on yield strength of 2080Al.

Figure 6. Influence of volume fraction of SiC particles on yield strength of 2080Al; comparing measurements and unit cell predictions.

Creep

Similar to observations on tensile strength, redistribution of stress from the matrix into reinforcement can lead to improvements in creep properties (12) and, in some cases, this can be readily predicted (13). For a matrix whose steady state creep rate when unreinforced is given by

$$\dot{\epsilon}^{creep} = A\sigma^n \quad (4)$$

where the coefficient A is a constant, the composite steady state creep rate is given by the same expression with the same value of n but with a different value of A_c . The ratio A_c/A is a measure of the improvement in creep strength resulting from incorporation of reinforcement. A_c/A depends only on the volume fraction and geometry of the reinforcing phase and is independent of the particle elastic moduli and the matrix elastic and initial plastic (e.g., monotonic strain hardening) properties. Unit cell model predictions such as those shown in Figure 7 suggest that the steady-state creep rate will decrease markedly as

volume fraction increases. The comparisons with experimental creep data shown in Figure 7 demonstrate the importance and system specificity of both direct and indirect strengthening. The unit cell model predicts quite well the improvements observed when spherical TiC particles are incorporated into precipitation hardened aluminum (2219Al) or solid solution strengthened aluminum alloys (Al-1.5Mg), demonstrating the importance of direct strengthening in these systems. In contrast, composites such as 2080Al/SiC and Al/TiC show pronounced indirect effects (14). The incorporation of as little as 10 volume percent SiC particles into 2080Al actually leads to a decrease in creep resistance compared to unreinforced 2080. This decrease in creep resistance is attributed to a stress-induced precipitate instability which occurs at elevated temperatures near the sharp corners of the angular SiC particles. Although creep resistance is degraded in the 2080Al/SiC system, increasing the volume fraction of SiC from 10-30% does lead to an improvement in creep resistance which is consistent with that predicted by unit cell models. Indirect effects can also be quite beneficial as shown in the case of pure Al/TiC which shows a dramatic improvement in creep resistance via changes in the mechanisms of dislocation network formation and migration.

Fatigue

Improvements in fatigue behavior are often suggested as an advantage of metal matrix composites, however fatigue is a complex process and our understanding of the influence of particle reinforcement on the fatigue strength of metals is quite limited. Many investigators have found that when stress-controlled experiments are used to characterize fatigue, the lives of particle reinforced metals are generally longer than those of unreinforced metals (15). These improvements are most pronounced at lower stresses, in the high cycle fatigue regime, as shown in Fig. 8. Decreasing particle size has been demonstrated to lead to marked increases in tensile strength and has also been reported to improved fatigue strength under stress control. Fatigue behavior can also be characterized by testing under strain control. Without exception when tests are conducted under total strain control the fatigue resistance of particle reinforced metals is inferior to that of the unreinforced metals. The relative importance of direct versus indirect strengthening on fatigue is unclear however the observed trends can be understood in a general way based on our understanding of the direct influence of reinforcement on elastic modulus, strength and work hardening. A more complete review of the various aspects of fatigue behavior of discontinuously reinforced metals, including the influence of reinforcement on cyclic deformation and fatigue crack propagation can be found in Ref. 15.

Figure 7. Influence of volume fraction of SiC particles on creep strength ratio; comparing experimental measurements (14) and unit cell predictions (13).

Figure 8. Influence of reinforcement on stress-controlled fatigue in 2080Al (9).

COST

For many engineering applications the cost of the manufactured component is an important and often deciding factor. It is clearly an important characteristic or property of a material and there is a need for including "cost" as an aspect of any composite design methodology. Important elements of cost of components fabricated from metal matrix composites include costs due to raw material, composite fabrication, shape forming, machining and recycling. Cost is also an empirically (and in some cases merely anecdotally) determined factor and the manufacturing databases which assist in accurate component cost models are only beginning to be developed for particle reinforced aluminum. In general, manufacturing cost increases with increasing volume fraction due to the difficulty to form and machine a finished component. Increasing volume fraction leads to more viscous molten metal, lower forgeability and increased machining costs. Decreasing particle size, however, can impact cost in quite different ways. Fine particles tend to be somewhat more expensive than coarse particles. Moreover, decreasing particle size leads to increasing viscosity in molten metals, thus making casting of fine particle composites quite difficult. Both of these factors lead to increased final part cost. In contrast, finer particles lead to increased ductility and thus improved forgeability. They also lead to substantial improvements in machinability thus increasing tool life and machining speeds and decreasing the cost for component machining.

APPLICATION TO THE CONNECTING ROD

This section provides an example of how what we loosely call a "methodology" can be used to select or design a particle reinforced metal composite for the connecting rod in an automotive engine (1). The important properties for an automotive engine connecting rod are fatigue resistance (load controlled), thermal expansion and low cost. A durable connecting rod requires a minimum value for the room temperature fatigue strength of 210MPa and a maximum CTE of $15 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$. Properties of secondary importance are modulus, ductility and creep resistance. Since typical operating temperatures are 150-180C, high strength aluminum alloys based on the Al-Cu-Mg system (e.g. 2080Al) are a reasonable matrix choice. These alloys can be heat treated to ensure thermal stability over this temperature range and have reasonable strengths. The fatigue properties and thermal expansion characteristics of these alloys are however deficient thus a metal matrix composite is a good candidate for this application. Reinforcement candidates include B_4C , SiC, Al_2O_3 and diamond, however both B_4C and diamond can be excluded for cost reasons. Both SiC and Al_2O_3 would be good choices, however, compared to Al_2O_3 , SiC has higher modulus (important for improving fatigue) and a much lower thermal expansion coefficient. Increasing the volume fraction of SiC improves CTE and fatigue strength. However, the need to manufacture this component cost effectively dictates that the volume fraction be limited to no more than 30%. Use of bounds suggests that a composite containing at least 15% SiC is required to meet the CTE requirements. Decreasing the particle size is an effective method for increasing the fatigue strength and decreasing the machining costs. It is therefore desirable to have a particle size which is as fine as possible. There are, however, limits since raw material costs increase as particle size decreases. For this application, a particle size of 4 to 9 μm appears to be a reasonable choice. Predictive models for fatigue strength are not yet available, however, experimentally it has been determined that a 2080Al alloy reinforced with 20% of SiC particles of 9 μm in size has a room temperature fatigue strength of 210MPa. Based on this exercise it appears that 2080Al/SiC/20p is a promising particle reinforced metal composite for the connecting rod.

SUMMARY

Some elements of a composite design "methodology" have been overviewed. This methodology has been shown to be reasonably straight forward for elastic and thermal properties. Because of the importance of indirect strengthening, strength-related properties require a more well-developed empirical knowledge base. This is especially true for creep and fatigue properties and also factors associated with the cost of component fabrication. Despite the limitations in our understanding of these factors, this methodology can provide guidelines for use by the material scientist in selection and development of promising particle reinforced metal composites.

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